

Traditional Agricultural Knowledge and Sustainable Agriculture Practice of Dhing Development Block: Assam, India

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Traditional agricultural knowledge is the age older practice of “judicial and sustainable use of knowledge, natural resources, traditional tools and cultural belief with little or no cost and is easily available. In this agricultural system interaction between humans and the environment is very close. Rural people highly depend on agricultural, and the use traditional farming techniques and do not prefer the use of modern farming inputs for high growth in productivity. People prefer the use of sustainable agricultural crops and methods So, in these areas environment is better than that of modern large scale commercial agriculture.

The study was conducted at a remote village Furhani Ati of Nagaon District to determines the traditional agricultural practices adopted by the farmers. There are 695 households from which 64 household sample survey was done. Data were collected by directed interview and group discussions among the farmer. The farmers use a total of 22 traditional tools and methods in farming practices. As the traditional agriculture is sustainable, it does not exert and adverse impact on environment. This study is to trace the traditional agricultural tools and a knowledge, used of which maintain sustainable development of agriculture. As a result, soil fertility almost remains constant.

Keywords: Age old practices, judicial, sustainable agriculture, traditional tools and methods, cultural belief, Furhani Ati, Nagaon.